

Towards a Sustainable Soil Information System in Togo (FertiTogo)

The Regional Hub for Fertilizer and Soil Health for West Africa and the Sahel

17-19 June 2025, Lome, Togo

Workshop report

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List of Abbreviation

MoA	Ministry of Agriculture
ITRA	Institut Togolais de Recherche Agronomique
SIS	Soil Information System
ISRIC	International Soil Reference and Information Centre
CABI	Centre for Agriculture and Bioscience International
IITA	International Institute of Tropical Agriculture
IFDC	International Fertilizer Development Center
OCP	Office Chérifien des Phosphates
UM6P	University Mohammed VI Polytechnic
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
DST	Decision Support Tool
GIS	Geographic Information System
ToT	Training of trainer
TU	Togo University
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
GIZ	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit GmbH
EU	European Union
ANA MET	Agence Nationale de la Météorologie du Togo
CFA	Communauté Financière Africaine
FEM	Fonds pour l'environnement mondial
AFD	Agence Française de Développement

Executive Summary

This SIS development report outlines the strategic steps for strengthening Togo's Soil Information System (FertiTogo) to enhance agricultural productivity, soil health, and informed decision-making for sustainable soil management. It builds on insights from the "Togo Soil Information System Development Workshop" held in June 2025 in Lome, Togo, hosted by Regional Hub for Fertilizer and Soil Health for West Africa and the Sahel, ITRA, MoA in Togo, ISRIC-World Soil Information, IFDC, IITA, and CABI. Participants from various sectors addressed common data and capacity challenges and discussed long-term financial sustainability options for FertiTogo.

The workshop reviewed seven components of the SIS framework, crucial for FertiTogo's success: 1) envisioning the SIS, 2) enabling environment, 3) needs assessment, 4) SIS ideal system design, 5) partnership development and sustainability plan, 6) data strategy, and 7) organizational and financial sustainability plan. The roadmap includes an overview of each component, addressing available information, gaps, and recommendations, which are optional for the FertiTogo project team to consider.

The key potential next steps for ITRA-MoA to consider include:

- Initiate formally contact with OCP Foundation and UM6P, with support from OCP A's representative in Togo to facilitate access to the existing SIS (FertiTogo) currently hosted at UM6P.
- Review the 2017 MoU between ITRA-MoA and the OCP Foundation to assess the possibility of transferring the hosting of FertiTogo from UM6P to Togo.
- Engage OCP Foundation and UM6P to develop a roadmap for the platform migration, if the Terms of Collaboration (ToC) outlined in the MoU permits it.
- Establish a steering and technical committees to define clear roles, responsibilities, and activities.
- Set up a financial sustainability plan, incorporating input from all relevant partners.
- Organize a validation workshop with broad stakeholder participation, once the design and work plans are in place and next steps are agreed upon.

The SIS owner and SIS operator (MoA/ITRA) intend to establish a governance and technical steering committee for the FertiTogo strengthening process. The committee will be responsible for setting strategic direction, overseeing system integrity, ensuring stakeholder coordination, guiding technical upgrades, and monitoring compliance with data governance and quality standards.

Acknowledgments

ITRA, MoA, ISRIC-World Soil Information, Regional Hub for Fertilizer and Soil Health for West Africa and the Sahel, and IFDC would like to thank workshop participants for their contributions that have led to the development of this roadmap. With special thanks to Regional Hub for Fertilizer and Soil Health for West Africa and the Sahel, and IFDC for their support in organizing the workshop, and to CABI for their input and review.

More information, supporting resources and useful tools for each of the components are available in the online SIS framework, hosted on ISRIC's Resource Library and created by CABI and ISRIC – World Soil Information (<https://resources.isric.org/sis-framework/>).

If there are any questions or aspects of the roadmap that require further support or input from ISRIC, kindly contact chrow.khurshid@isric.org or thaisa.vanderwoude@isric.org

Introduction

A Soil Information System (SIS) is not just a digital platform but a collaborative tool that engages stakeholders, from government agencies, universities, NGOs, private companies interested by the SIS, to farmers. It is helpful to improve data access, soil health management, and informed decision-making in Togo's agriculture sector. Understanding how these people and institutions should work together, and aligning on who is responsible for what, is a critical step to ensuring the progress of the SIS. There are three levels to consider: the individual (suitable skills, knowledge, competencies, and attitudes), the organizational (efficient structures, processes, and procedures), and the governmental level (establishment of adequate institutions, laws, and regulations).

[CAB-International](#) and [ISRIC – World Soil Information](#), supported by the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, has created a framework for SIS development, assessing these levels at the start of a SIS intervention. [SIS Framework](#) helps to identify activities needed to fulfil the SIS objectives, deciding also on the sequence in which these activities are best performed, who is going to do them, and identifying potential risks, with each specifically tailored to the country context. The SIS framework was the base for the FertiTogo development workshop which was held in June 2025 in Lome, Togo.

The objectives of the FertiTogo development workshop were:

- Enhancing accessibility and public usability of the current SIS.
- Exploring technical options (software, hosting) for sustainable operation.
- Identifying capacity gaps and training needs.
- Identify if other data is available from government, research institutions
- Identifying ways for developing a financially sustainable SIS.
- Identifying key partners that need to be involved in the development of a full-scale SIS
- Agreeing on next steps for the development of the SIS

This document gathers the information collected and validated during the workshop and proposes a suggested plan for implementing FertiTogo that details the steps required to achieve a specific goal. In this instance, the goal is a sustainable national SIS in Togo that will last beyond the initial phases of project funding, be built on best practices, and will continue to meet the needs of users.

Workshop Day 1:

The workshop commenced with welcome remarks from the director of the extension services ICAT in replacement of the General Secretary of MoA who was busy, IFDC, and IITA. This was followed by an introduction of participants and an overview of the program and its expected outputs by ISRIC -World Soil Information.

Session 1 – Benefits of using the SIS framework

Chrow- from ISRIC presented the SIS framework, a brief explanation on what is FAIR data, the FAIR process framework, and why is FAIR good for soil data projects. This followed by a Q&A session with the participants.

Session 2 – Current state of Togo SIS and Live demo

Dr Kossi Koudjega, one of the focal points of the government for the Regional Hub in Togo and Mr Esso ASSIH-FARAM, the SIG ans soil mapping specialist from ITRA have presented the current state of Togo SIS and a live demo of the current platform:

- FertiTogo targeted 62% of the available agricultural land in Togo, representing 3.60 million hectares.
- The existing FertiTogo system was funded by the government through the Vulnerable Populations Support Program (PAPV) and received technical and financial support from the OCP Foundation and FAO in 2019.
- Soil surveys were conducted across several regions in Togo between 2017 and 2020,.
- Soil maps were generated the combined effort of both parties based on the survey results for five laboratory-analyzed properties (e.g., pH, P, K, OM, an EC.).
- Mapping resolution was 1 km² per map unit.
- Two teams, each consisting of 8 members, were mobilized to collect soil samples covering a total of 2 226 100 ha representing 62% of the Togolese agricultural lands.
- Samples were collected at a depth of 0-20 cm.
- A total of 19905 soil samples were analyzed at ITRA using national standard laboratory protocols.
- Analysed parameters included pH, phosphorus (P), potassium (K), organic matter (OM), and an Electrivity conductivity .
- Based on the results, fertilizer recommendations were developed and are available on the FertiTogo portal: www.fertitogo.tg
- Togo received capacity-building training from UM6P, focusing on:
 1. Data collection techniques
 2. Technical and IT skills

3. Laboratory analysis procedures
- Main challenges in the current FertiTogo:
 1. The platform www.fertitogo.tg faces security access issues and requires a license update, which must be resolved by UM6P, the hosting institution.
 2. Soil and crop data are not centralized; currently stored in Excel files on a private computer, which limits accessibility and data security.
 3. Technical issues and platform maintenance can only be handled by UM6P, and the response time is often slow.
 4. There is no direct communication between ITRA and UM6P; all interactions must go through the OCP Foundation, creating delays.
 5. ITRA lacks at the moment the financial, human, and technical resources to independently host, maintain, or further develop the platform.
 6. A national-level data sharing agreement is needed between key institutions such as Togo University (TU) and international organizations that hold Togo-related data through various projects.
 - Main objectives for FertiTogo in the future are:
 1. Ensure FertiTogo is fully owned and maintained by the MoA through ITRA.
 2. Develop and update soil fertility maps to support agricultural development in Togo.
 3. Conduct soil health assessments to determine fertilizer needs and guide sustainable soil management.
 4. Design and implement decision support tools (DST) for fertilizer application and crop planning.

Session 3 – Ideal System Design

Chrow from ISRIC-World Soil Information presented the Soil information Workflow (SIWF). The objectives of this session were to brainstorm the ideal system design-based pilot and determine the key functionalities. Below questions were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- What specific functionalities or features (e.g. dashboards, maps, data security, mobile accessibility, offline access) is missing from the current SIS?
- What are you expecting the SIS to serve you?
- What are the technical and digital literacy gaps (among users)?

Three groups, each consisting of 5 to 6 participants, were formed to discuss the topic using the questions provided. A summary of the group discussions is outlined below:

- The current FertiTogo platform lacks several essential features, including:
 1. Data security
 2. Mobile accessibility

3. Offline functionality
 4. Interactive dashboards
 5. Map viewers and visualization tools
 6. User guides and operational manuals
- FertiTogo is expected to fulfil multiple roles, including:
 1. Fertilizer formulation
 2. Spatial data and modelling
 3. Updated soil data
 4. Agroecological information
 5. Climate data and crops data.
 - Supporting users in both the official language and local languages to ensure broader accessibility and usability.
 - The hosting team currently lacks the technical and infrastructure capacities to effectively maintain and further develop the platform.
 - Additionally:
 1. Training of Trainers (ToT) is essential to transfer knowledge to other Soil Information System (SIS) users.
 2. Make the SIS platform simple and user-friendly to improve accessibility.
 3. Offline access is a key requirement for users in areas with limited connectivity.
 4. An updated and comprehensive training curriculum is crucial to support long-term use and sustainability of the platform.

Session 4 – SIS stakeholder map and requirements

The objective of this session was to identify the user requirements and use cases beyond fertility maps, soil degradation monitoring, and others. Below questions were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- Who are potential users and data producers?
- What decisions do potential users need to take that require (or would benefit from) soil data?
- Define SIS requirements to address the needs; why would they use a SIS?
- What are capacity building needs of users?

Group composition:

Group 1: Participants from ITRA

Group 2: Participants from the Ministry of Agriculture (MoA)

Group 3: Participants from IITA, IFDC, and OCP representatives

Discussions were initiated using a set of guiding questions related to FertiTogo.

Key outcomes from group discussions:

- Potential users and data producers of FertiTogo:
 1. Decision makers
 2. Researchers and lecturers
 3. Extension officers
 4. Private sector companies
 5. Funding and development organizations
 6. Farmers' organizations
 7. Media representatives

- Uses of soil data via FertiTogo:
 1. Supporting land use planning and promotion of best agricultural practices
 2. Designing research studies and field trials
 3. Making fertilizer recommendations
 4. Strategic planning for institutions and long-term development goals

- User needs and recommendations:
 1. FertiTogo should provide available, accessible, and regularly updated soil data
 2. The platform should also include data on crops, climate, pollution, and other relevant parameters
 3. Data standardization and harmonization are essential to ensure consistency and interoperability
 4. Establish a data sharing agreement between:
 - ❖ Data producers (research institutions, universities, international organizations, funded projects)
 - ❖ Data users (e.g., decision makers, development partners)
 5. Develop a data policy by the SIS owner to guide responsible use and access
 6. Develop a sustainable funding strategy and business model to support long-term SIS maintenance and development

- Governance and system management:
 1. Establish a multi-stakeholder governance framework to ensure inclusive and sustainable SIS management
 2. Clearly define roles and responsibilities for national institutions involved in the SIS ecosystem
 3. Explore alternative system architectures that enhance functionality, scalability, and security
 4. Provide technical support to the hosting and development team by Ministry of Digital Economy and Ministry of Agriculture.

- Accessibility and capacity building:
 1. Ensure the platform is multilingual, including availability in local languages
 2. Invest in capacity building in areas such as:
 - ❖ Data management

- ❖ Information dissemination and service delivery
- ❖ System usage and maintenance

Session 5 – Data requirements

The objective of this session was to identify the data challenges. Below questions were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- How should user permissions and data access be managed?
- What are the data challenges?
- What are the data requirements from user perspective?
- What data policies, strategies and mandates exist?
- How can data sharing be achieved between SIS related efforts?
- How can the FAIR data principles strengthen the SIS?

Summary of group discussions:

Each of the three groups (5–6 participants per group) used guiding questions to explore the topic. Key advice from all group discussions are summarized below:

- Provide a clear framework for data sharing to guide the use and exchange of data through FertiTogo.
- Include a standardized form at the SIS platform for users to request specific data.
- Manage access to sensitive or restricted data through a formal request process directed to the SIS administrative unit.
- Strengthening the data security protocols to protect both public and sensitive datasets.
- Ensure data quality control measures are in place and that all datasets are regularly updated.
- Create a centralized data repository to efficiently store, manage, and serve soil and related datasets.
- Establish national policies and legal frameworks to govern data management and sharing practices.
- There is a need to establish formal Memorandums of Understanding (MoUs) and data sharing agreements between national institutions to:
 1. Centralize data storage and access
 2. Ensure data quality and consistency
 3. Facilitate coordinated and secure data management

Workshop Day 2:

Welcoming and reflections from day one was carried on by IITA, IFDC, and ISRIC.

Session 1- Future of the SIS

The objective of this session was to explore future hosting of the SIS and what would be technically and organizationally feasible. Below questions were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- **Future of the SIS - Risks of the Current Setup**
 1. What are the risks of continuing to rely on an externally hosted and controlled platform?
 2. What happens if UM6P discontinues support or access?
 3. How resilient is the system to disruptions, including cyber-security or policy-related risks?

- **Future of the SIS - Future Hosting Scenarios**
 1. What technical and institutional options exist for relocating or duplicating the SIS?
 2. Hosting in a Togolese government institution (e.g., Ministry server)?
 3. National research institution or university?
 4. Cloud-based hosting (e.g., AWS, Azure, African cloud services)?

- **Future of the SIS - Ownership and Governance**
 1. Who should be the long-term technical administrator of the SIS?
 2. What capacities are needed for this entity (e.g., IT support, GIS skills, cybersecurity)?
 3. How can the technical ownership align with institutional ownership?
 4. Which institution in Togo should be responsible for the long-term technical and financial management of the SIS?

Summary of group discussions:

Each group (5–6 participants) explored the topic using guiding questions. Key insights from all three groups are outlined below:

- Current hosting challenges:
 1. The current hosting of FertiTogo by an external partner (UM6P, outside Togo) presents a risk of data loss or data damaged.
 2. The setup is not sustainable, with high risks related to:
 - ❖ Timely data management
 - ❖ Data updates
 - ❖ Technical issue resolution

- ❖ Political changes between the two countries may jeopardize access to the platform and its data.
- Proposed hosting transition:
 1. In the near future, migrate the SIS platform from UM6P to the National Data Centre under the Ministry of Digital Economy.
 2. This centre currently has the technical and human capacity to temporarily host the platform.
 3. In the long term, ITRA–MoA is expected to become the official host and owner of FertiTogo.
 4. Support for migration and hosting can be provided by:
 - ❖ National Digital Agency
 - ❖ IT department at MoA
 - ❖ National Agency for Cybersecurity
 - ❖ Public-private partnerships
 - ❖ These entities should work in close coordination with ITRA to ensure successful migration and maintenance.

- Ownership and governance:

Two ownership options were discussed:

1. **Option 1:** Directorate of Planning of Agricultural Statistics (DPSSE) under MoA
2. **Option 2:** ITRA under MoA .
This option was agreed upon by stakeholders. ITRA will serve as the institutional owner of FertiTogo. Within ITRA, the soil program theme will act as the host and administrative unit for FertiTogo. This unit will coordinate with other MoA departments on:
 - ❖ Administrative procedures
 - ❖ Legal frameworks
 - ❖ Funding and financial management

Technical support will primarily be provided by the Data Lab Directorate at the Ministry of Digital Economy.

- Governance structure:

Two main committees will be established:

1. Administrative, financial, and legal Committee

Members may include representatives from:

- ❖ Secretary General, MoA
- ❖ Ministry of Digital Economy
- ❖ Ministry of Economy and Finance
- ❖ Ministry of Planning

- ❖ Ministry of Environment
- ❖ ITRA – MoA

2. Technical and scientific committee

Members may include representatives from:

- ❖ ITRA
- ❖ MoA
- ❖ Ministry of Digital Economy
- ❖ Ministry of Economy and Finance
- ❖ Togo University (TU)

Session 2- Long term sustainability

The objective of this session was to explore financial strategies to ensure the long-term sustainability of FertiTogo. Below questions were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- **Long term sustainability - Cost Structure – Understanding Financial Needs**
 1. What are the key cost categories in the SIS lifecycle (e.g. personnel, tech infrastructure, data management, capacity building)?
 2. What is the estimated cost for the next 1–3 years across the next development phases that the SIS will need to go through (initiation, design, implementation)
 3. Which costs are already covered (e.g. by the government, OCP Foundation) and which are still unfunded?
- **Long term sustainability - Blending Core and Value-Added Financing**
 1. What government budget lines could potentially support the SIS (e.g. agriculture, digital infrastructure, environment)?
 2. Could a dedicated SIS funding unit or fundraising mechanism (e.g. grant writing team, PPP unit) be established?
- **Long term sustainability - Revenue Streams and Public-Private Collaboration**
 1. What services or information could the SIS tailor for private sector clients (e.g. fertilizer companies, agribusinesses)?
 2. What types of users (e.g. extension agents, local governments, NGOs) would be willing to pay for enhanced, user-specific data?
 3. Are there existing consulting, training, or soil analysis services that SIS could build upon to generate income?

Summary of group discussions:

Three groups (each with 5–6 participants) discussed the financial and funding aspects of FertiTogo. The key findings are summarized below:

- Key cost categories in the FertiTogo lifecycle:
 1. Staffing and human resources
 2. Soil and crop data collection
 3. Data management and regular updates
 4. Technical infrastructure and hosting
 5. System maintenance and troubleshooting
 6. Soil sample analysis costs
 7. Laboratory equipment and operations
 8. Capacity development and training programs

- Estimated costs for the next development phases (1–3 Years):

Note: These estimates are indicative and may vary based on stakeholder capacity and contributions.

1. Initiation phase: 800 million CFA
2. Design and development phase: 300 million CFA
3. Implementation phase: 500 million CFA

- Funding Status:
 1. Covered by government:
 - ❖ Part of the initial design and launch of the platform

 2. Not yet covered:
 - ❖ System maintenance
 - ❖ Platform redesign and updates
 - ❖ Implementation of additional functionalities
 - ❖ Communication and platform management
 - ❖ Capacity development activities
 - ❖ Estimated cost for the above: 300–500 million CFA

- Potential government budget support:

Funding could potentially be allocated from the Ministry of Agriculture (MoA) and the Ministry of Digital Economy.

- Proposed financial mechanisms and structures:
 1. Establish a dedicated SIS funding unit to manage financial sustainability.
 2. Generate income from both national and international users
 3. Secure core funding contributions from relevant ministries' budgets
 4. Potential fundraising mechanisms in future, once the SIS is fully functioning:
 - ❖ Apply user fees for premium services and consultancy using SIS resources
 - ❖ Charge access fees for specific data sets
 - ❖ Introduce platform access fees for certain types of users

- Public-Private collaboration opportunities:
 1. Partner with fertilizer companies to support and improve fertilizer formulation using SIS data
 2. Collaborate with agro-industry companies for applied use of soil and crop data
 3. Engage with farmers' organizations, extension agencies, and international NGOs for:
 - ❖ Soil sample analysis through ITRA laboratories
 - ❖ Service-based income generation for FertiTogo
 - ❖ Offer consultancy services related to:
 - a. Soil and crop data interpretation
 - b. Fertilizer recommendations
 - c. Decision support systems

Session 3- Partnership model

Below questions were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- Who are the critical partners needed to successfully implement and maintain the SIS in Togo?
- What roles should each stakeholder group play in the SIS ecosystem?
- What institutional arrangement or coordination mechanism is needed to govern the partnership?
- How can we ensure that the partnership is inclusive, transparent, and responsive to stakeholder needs over time?
- What agreements or commitments (e.g. MoUs, data-sharing protocols) are needed to formalize the collaboration?

In a panel discussion, the participants identified critical partners in FertiTogo as below:

1. National entities: Ministry of Digital Economy, Ministry of Planning, Ministry of Environment, National agency for meteorology ANA MET.
2. Togo University TU
3. Private sectors such as fertilizer companies, and OCP Africa
4. UM6P
5. IFDC
6. IITA

Potential partners' role in FertiTogo were defined as below:

1. Technical support and capacity development: Ministry of Digital Economy, UM6P, OCP A, IFDC, IITA, ISRIC, FAO.
2. Funders: WB, FAO, OCP A, IFDC, IITA, FAO, GIZ, FIDA, FEM EU, AFD, Ministry of Planning, Ministry of Environment (Providing budget line), Private fertilizer companies,
3. Data supplier: Togo university TU, national and private research institutes, OCP A, UM6P, Ministry of Environment, MoA.
4. Data users: MoA, Ministry of Environment, other ministries, private sector and agricultural, fertilizer companies, farmer association platforms and extension services.

Coordination and partnership model: The participants agreed on establishing two steering committees:

1. Technical steering committee: ITRA leading this committee as SIS owner.
2. National steering committee: MoA leading this committee as SIS owner.
3. Members in above committees are identified in section: **Future of the SIS - Ownership and Governance.**
4. Agreement between national partners in these committees to be via MoU.

Session 4- Next steps

Below questions were used to identify the next steps for FertiTogo with the stakeholders' groups:

- What are the immediate action items based on the discussions in the previous sessions?
- Which short-term priorities should be addressed first, and what is the timeline for each?
- Who will be responsible for each key action, and how can accountability be ensured?
- What are the key milestones for FertiTogo over the next 6, 12 and 24 months?

The actions are provided in the table below.

Table 1 Action points

Action point	Account-able (the institution "responsible" reports to)	Respon-sible (assigned to carry out the task)	Support	Timeline	Priority level 1=high 2=medium 3=low	Mile-stone? Y/N
Unlock the access to the current FertiTogo platform	ITRA/MoA	ITRA	MoA, OCP A, OCP foundation, UM6P	1-4 weeks	High	
Re-visit the MoU between ITRA and OCP foundation signed in 2017	ITRA/MoA	ITRA	NA	1-4 weeks	High	
Signing data sharing agreement with ISRIC and the Hub to share the data in order to generate updated maps for Togo	ITRA/MoA ,	ITRA	IFDC/ WA Hub	1-4 weeks	High	
Initiate discussion with OCP foundation and UM6P to migrate the data and the platform to Togo	ITRA/MoA	ITRA	Ministry of Digital Economy, MoA, OCP A	1-3 months	Medium	
Initiate discussion on building two steering committees	ITRA/MoA	ITRA	MoA, IFDC/ WA Hub	1-3 months	Medium	

Annex 1: Workshop Program

Welcome and registration | 09:00 - 09:30

Session 1: setting the scene | 09:30 -10:00

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
3'	Welcome by Moderator	Goals and format for the workshop <i>The moderator will introduce each speaker before they speak</i>
10'	Ministry of Agriculture / ITRA SG MAHVDR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome remarks Soil degradation in Togo The need for understanding best practice in the development of soil information systems The motivation of the government to develop and own a fully functioning SIS
5'	IFDC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The need for a SIS to provide better fertiliser recommendations in Togo
5'	OCP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drivers for having supported the development of a SIS pilot in Togo Aspirations for long term scalability and financial sustainability beyond their initial support
5'	IITA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation of the West Africa Hubs project Goals for the workshop and how it fits with the project activities and goals
2'	Moderator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Key takeaways from initial presentations

Session 2: Introduction to the SIS framework | 10:00 - 10:30

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
3'	Moderator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction, objectives and format of the session
20'	Dr. Lydiah Gatere CABI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction to the Framework for Sustainable National Soil Information Systems (SIS Framework) Value of FAIR data principles for SISs
5'	Q&A from the audience Moderator	

Group photo and coffee break | 10:30-11:00

Session 3: Current status of SIS and live demo | 11:00 – 12:00

Objective: To present the current capabilities and limitations of the existing pilot SIS.

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
2'	Moderator	Session Introduction
5'	Ministry of Agriculture / ITRA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current state of soil information pilot in Togo • Plans and goals for FertiTogo in the long term
35'	OCP	<p>Live walkthrough of existing SIS (platform or mockup)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the current technical setup of the SIS hosted at UM6P? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ What platform/software is it built on (e.g., CMS, database type)? ◦ What components (frontend/backend, GIS engine, etc.) make up the system? • What soil parameters and data formats are currently managed within the system? • Who currently has access to the system (administrative, user, viewer levels)? • What are the current functionalities in the SIS?
20'	Q&A from the audience Moderator	
3'	Moderator	Key takeaways and preparation for action planning

Session 4: Ideal system design | 12:00 – 13:00

Objective: To understand the requirements and expectations of Togo SIS users to inform the design of technically feasible, user-friendly, and scalable architecture that is FAIR data compliant.

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
5'	Moderator	Session Introduction
10'	Chrow Khurshid ISRIC	Soil Information Workflow: possible elements of a SIS
45'	Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What specific functionalities or features (e.g. dashboards, maps, data security, mobile accessibility, offline access) is missing from the current SIS? • What are you expecting the SIS will serve you? • What are the technical and digital literacy gaps (among users)?

Networking lunch | 13:00-14:00

Session 5: SIS stakeholder map and requirements | 14:00 – 15:00

Objective: To identify the user requirements and use cases beyond fertility maps, soil degradation monitoring, and others

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
2'	Moderator	Session Introduction
55'	Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who are the potential users and (data) producers? • What decisions do potential users need to take that require (or would benefit from) soil data? • Define SIS requirements to address the needs; why would they use a SIS? • What are capacity building needs of users?
3'	Moderator	Key takeaways and preparation for action planning

Session 6: Data requirements | 15:00 – 16:00

Objective: to identify the data challenges

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
2'	Moderator	Session Introduction
55'	Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How should user permissions and data access be managed? • What are the data challenges? • What are the data requirements from user perspective? • What data policies, strategies and mandates exist? • How can data sharing be achieved between SIS related efforts? • How can the FAIR data principles strengthen the SIS?
3'	Moderator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key takeaways

Close of day 1 | 16:00 – 16:30

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
2'	Moderator	
5'	Ministry of Agriculture / ITRA	Key takeaways from day 1
5'	IITA	
3'	Moderator	Official closure of day 1

Annex 2: Flipcharts from different groups

- G1

① Structure des coûts

- Le personnel, l'infrastructure tech, gestion de données, le renforcement des Capacités
- Collecte de données, Maintenance, Analyse des échantillons
- Voir ultérieurement avec l'équipe de l'ITRA
- Coûts déjà couverts: Lancement, mise en oeuvre, conception
- Coûts qui ne sont pas couverts: maintenance évolutive, Renforcement de capacité, Communication, coût de migratⁿ de l'hébergement, fonctionnalité

② Modèles de financement

- Agriculture, Ministère de l'économie numérique
- Projet-Programme de développement
- Oui

③ Source de revenus et collaboratⁿ Public-Privé

- Les besoins en fonction des matières de fertilité du sol suivant les différentes zones de production (agros)
- Informatⁿ sur les essais
- Info sur les zones de production, types de cultures (agros-industrie)
- Planificatⁿ des activités (ONG), partenaires techniques)

- T5

- G1

- Les industries agroalimentaire,
- les producteurs et distributeurs d'engrais,
- Les institutions régionales de recherche, ...

(Informatⁿ et Formatⁿ)

- ICAT Public-Privé
- Instituts d'encadrement des producteurs (ICAT et autres)
- Laboratoire des sols de l'ITRA (Analyses)

G1 - Data Requirement

- Créer un cadre de données et utilisations de données.
- Créer un cadre de données, qualité des données, qualité des données et qualité des données pour la production agricole, actualité des données.
- Fiabilité et qualité des données.
- Structure nationale de digitalisation de services de données en cas d'urgence.
- Créer un cadre de données de partage des données.
- Créer un cadre de données et l'architecture de système.
- Permettre la données pour faciliter l'opérationnel.
- Permettre le partage entre plusieurs partenaires.

G2 - Data Requirement

- Catégoriser les données et les utilisateurs
 - mise en place d'une gouvernance
 - mise en place d'une procédure d'accès et de gestion des données. (Formulaire de demande, lettre de demande aux administr.
- Souveraineté, Sécurisation des données.
 - Financement pour la collecte des données
 - Précision des données.
 - Mise à jour des données, Automatisation des données.
- Accès facile, données précises, données sur les paramètres climatiques.
 - Loi sur les données.
 - Politique nationale par IA
 - PND et Feuille de Route
- Mutualisation des données
 - MU (Membre, données d'accord).
- Disponibilité en temps réel
 - Actualisation des données.
 - Fiabilité des données.
 - Souplesse dans la collecte de données, l'interprétation, et l'utilisation par les bénéficiaires financiers locaux.

G3 - Data Requirement

- Création d'une cellule d'autorisation d'accès
 - Création d'un compte d'accès
 - Avoir un administrateur pour la gestion de compte des utilisateurs au IITA/UR
- Centralisation des données existantes.
 - Collecte des données complémentaires et
 - Actualisation des données existantes
 - qualité de données
- Qualité, fiabilité, accessibilité de données
- Faciliter l'existence de politique de gestion de données au niveau national.
- A travers des conventions de collaborations ou protocoles d'accord
-

A Data Requirements

Summary of 3-groups

- 1) Framework for data sharing
Administration unit to give access
Form for users to fill and ask for data.
- 2) Lack of Data Security
Updated Data
Easy access data
Finance
Reliable data + accurate data
Central Repository to serve data.

3- good quality data
→ updated data, accurate, reliable data
→ Easy access data.

B Data Requirements

- 4) There are enough national laws and policies for Data management + Data sharing data.
- 5) MoU / Data sharing agreements / framework.
→ Regulation and Laws
- 6) use different platform
access data easily
Updated data

G1 Ideal system Design

- 1) - No Offline service
- Lack of the domestication of the server
- No way to refresh and upgrade data (Non-dynamic)
- No Satellite view
- 2) - Give information on soil micronutrients
- Give information on agroecological area and Bio-farming area (When can we use these practices)
- Use satellite data to improve
- Having time interval for updating SIS
- Integrate voice note or record in local language on good practice
- 3) - Train more farmers, advisors
- Integrate digital information training in University

G2

Reponses SA

- Sécurité des données
- Accessibilité aussi bien physique que hors ligne
- Manuel de Procédure ou Guide d'utilisation (Tutoriel), FAQ
- Formulation d'engrais par Site et spéculati
- Travaux de modélisation temporelle et spatiale

- Sensibilisation des utilisateurs
- En absence des Smartphone et la connexion
- Interopérabilité / connectivité
- Hébergement / domestication.

G3

- 1) - offline access (accès impossible sans Internet)
- mobile accessibility
- 2) - Rendre plus dynamique la plate forme
- Que la plateforme ressorte les types et les doses d'engrais en lien avec les spéculations
- Intégrer les prévisions météorologiques
- 3) - Accès à l'Internet la plate forme online sans connexion Internet.

(A) Data Requirements Summary of 3 groups

- Framework for data sharing
Administration want to give access
Form for users to fill and ask for data.
- Lack of Data Security
Updated Data
Easy access data
Finance
Reliable data + accurate data
Central Repository to serve data.
- good quality data
up dated data, accurate, reliable data.
Easy access data.

(B) Data Requirements

- There are enough national laws and policies for Data management + Data sharing data.
- Mold / Data sharing agreements / Frame work.
Regulation and Laws
- use different platform
access data easily
up dated data

- ministère de l'économie numérique et de la transformation digitale
 - ministère de l'environnement
 - Universités publiques
 - PTF (FAO, GIZ, IFDC, OCP...)
 - ANAMET / secteurs privés
 - IITA, ISRIC (les instituts Internat. canaux de recherches)
- Producteurs de données - universités pub
Institut de Recherche
Utilisateurs de données - ICAT
les ministères
les PTF
secteurs privés
ETOP
- Les bailleurs de fonds - les PTF
- Développeurs techniques - OCP, ISRIC
ESA-UL
IITA
- Coordinateurs et facilitateurs de politiques - les ministères
- Un comité de pilotage présidé par le ministère de l'agriculture et un groupe de travail technique dirigé par l'ITRI

SIS MAHYDR (Sécurité, maintenance)

- MENTD**: Hébergement, Support tech
- F.OCP/UMOP**: Migration de données, Accompagnement tech.
- IITA PTF ISRIC IFDC**
- M.P.et**
- Accord de Partenariat Universités**: Fournir des données, Pré-alimenter le SIS, Support tech
- Accord de partenariat Public-Privé**: Entreprises Privées (OCP, Fertisistem...), Fabrication d'engrais, Aspect financier

G2 -

I. Structure des Coûts

A) Personnel :

- Coordonnateur du SIS (existe à l'ITRA.)
- Administrateur de SIS
- Gestionnaire de données
- Dev/opp pour applications
- Agents de Collecte de Données

2. Infrastructure technique

- Serveur Cloud, disque dur externe
- Logiciel (Arcgis, Qgis, ...)
- PC, Kit d'analyse mobile, GPS, tablette
- Equipements de Laboratoire, Réactifs et Consommables
- Maintenance des équipements.

3. Gestion des Données

- Coût est inclus dans (D) et (E)

4. Renforcement des Capacités

- Formation du personnel
- Formation des utilisateurs

B. Coût pour les 1 à 3 prochaines années

- ~~Collecte de~~ initiation des utilisateurs → 800.17 (suite)
- développement → 300 M.
- mise en oeuvre → 500 M.

C. Coût couverts

- Gouvernement | 800 M.
- et
- FOCP |
- FAO |

Coût non couverts | 300 et 500 M.

II. Modèle de financement

- 1- Budget de l'Agriculture, de l'économie numérique, l'environnement; Planification
- ligne de SIS
- 2- Oui chaque ministère doit décider un fond ou SIS

III. Source de Revenus et Collaboration Public-Privé

- 1)
 - Abonnement
 - carte d'aptitude Culturelle
 - Conseil technique
 - Formulation d'engrais
2.
 - Entreprise d'engrais.
 - Agro Industries...
 - Opérateurs Privés
- 3- Oui (Labo, ITRA)

A) Stakeholders map and Requirements Summary of 3-groups

- 1 Decision makers
 - Researchers + Lectures
 - Extension officers
 - private companies
 - Funders
 - Development organizations
 - Media for awareness
 - farmer organisations.
- 2 - *to do research
 - * for best land management and practices
 - * Fertilizer recommendation
 - * Strategic plan and long term goals.
- 3 -> updated data + Available data
 - > Easy access data
 - > standardized + harmonized data
 - > Data sharing agreements
 - > Data policies
 - > Sustainable funding mechanisms
 - > crop soil + climate + pollution model.

B) Stakeholders map and Requirements

- 1 Multi governance that bring national stakeholders to maintain and manage SIS.
- 2 Identify different roles for national institutions in SIS.
 - > Legal framework for how to share data /
 - > Technical Supports.
 - > Different languages
 - > Explore different system architectures.
- 3 -> Tools
 - > Data management
 - > Data series
 - > awareness /
 - > serving information for
 - > How to use the system & maintain

Ownership of SIS (A)

- DP SSE -
Director of planning of MoA
of Agricultural Statistics - MoA

two option 1

- Committees from different government partners.

Togo SIS

Committee 1
management policies
finance ↓

Committee 2
Technical
IT
GIS
Soil Science ↓

→ SG - MoA
→ Mo - Digital economy
→ Mo - Finance and Finance
→ Mo - planning
→ Mo - Environment
→ ITRA

→ Mo - Digital Economy
→ MoA
→ ITRA
→ TU
→ Economic Stim

Ownership SIS option 2 (Is Agreed)

Technical owner - ITRA ✓
Institutional owner - MoA ✓

How to Align?

Soil programme at ITRA (Can be used as Unit) for Administration (Coordination) with MoA

Technical needs → Support with ministry of Digital economy - (Directory called - Data Lab)

→ ITRA don't have any Technical capacity.

ITRA + TU

Utilisateurs
Chercheurs, Agents de vulgarisation; fournisseurs d'intrants (engrais...); les décideurs politiques, Etudiants, Enseignants
ONG Agricole,

Producteurs de données
- Institution de Recherche, Universités les O.
Service de Météo, l'environnement, Mines

② Amélioration de la Productivité agricole
- Gestion durable des terres
- Connaître les zones potentielles et les cultures spécifiques
- Elaboration des projets agricoles
- Planification des zones de Reboisement,
- Implantation des Usines de Transformation
- Travaux de Recherches

③ Facilité d'accès, fiabilité des données
- Actualisation des données.

4 Formation des Utilisateurs
- etc

MoA

① UTILISATEURS
- Chercheurs
- OP
- Services d'encadrement technique (vulgarisation)
- Centre de formation agricole
- Les producteurs d'engrais
- Métriers

② Producteurs des données
Chercheurs, Les Services de vulgarisation, Services de statistiques agricoles.

② Décisions
- Choisir le type d'engrais et la dose
- Choix de la spécialisation
- Choix des bonnes pratiques
- orientations stratégiques de l'Etat.

③ Exigences du SIS
- données disponibles et fiables, etc
- données accessibles, actualisables
- système adaptable en temps continu.

④ Besoins des utilisateurs
- Maîtrise de l'utilisation du système
- Renforcement des capacités en maintenance du système en gestion des bases de données du système. Pour l'intégration des données
- Renforcement de capacités des vulgarisateurs sur la collecte de données du SIS

OCP + IITA + IFDC

① POTENTIAL USERS & PRODUCERS
- AGRIC. ADVISORS
- PRIVATE SECTOR (agronomists, planters, Fertilizer companies)
- POLICY MAKERS
- DEVELOPMENT ORG. (IFDC, FAO, GIZ...)
- FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS

② RESEARCH INST. (ITRA, UNIVERSITIES...)
- FERTILIZER ORGANIZATION (COSTOP)

② DECISION MAKING.
- BUYING, SELLING, FORMALIZATION FERTILIZER-
SUPPORTING DECISIONS
- SUPPORT UPDATING
- PLANNING, ENVIRONMENTAL DEVELOP.
- LAND USE PLANNING

③ SIS SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS
- EASE OF ACCESS
- ACQUISITION INFORMATION
- COST BENEFIT ANALYSIS
- SUSTAINABILITY OF THE SYSTEM

④ USER CAPACITY NEEDS
- TRAINING GUIDANCE ON SYSTEM FUNCTIONS
- INCREASE AWARENESS

Ideal System Design

Summary 3-groups

- 1- Everything in Q1 are missing from TogoSIS
 - + Guidelines
 - + Manuals

Dashboard!

- 2- Expectation of SIS
 - 1- ~~Ag~~ Fertilizer formulation
 - 2- ~~Special~~ modelling : -/+ ^{temporal} modelling
Spatial modelling + Alert on soil state?
 - 3- Agroecological information
 - 4- Updated soil data
 - 5- In local language.
 - 6- more dynamic platform/ ^{Climate data + crop}

3- (1) TOT / capacity building / offline access / data

→ Simple format update curriculum
to access the platform + Train Farmer + Technique

G3

* Structure des coûts - Comprendre les besoins financiers

- le personnel, l'infrastructure technique
- la gestion des données, le renforcement des capacités, maintenance et mise à jour des données, Collecte logistique
- ~~Coûts~~ PT (par mémoire, Etude)
- Δ Coûts couverts (Gouvernement, OCP, FAO...)
- Collecte de données
- Analyses au laboratoire
- formation des agents
- le personnel
- Supports logistiques (matériel roulant, informatiques, laboratoire)
- Plate forme fertilisants
- maintenance de la plate forme
- Δ Coûts non encore couverts
- Actualisation des données
- licence de sécurité
- formation de nouveaux agents
- hébergement local de la plate forme
- maintenance

G3

* Modèles de financement - mélange de financement de base et de financement à Valeur ajoutée

- Agriculture et l'infrastructure numérique
- Owi,

* Sources de Revenus et Collaboration public - privée

- Familles de recommandation des engrais adaptés aux types de sols et les quantités
- Services météorologiques
- types de cultures en fonction des sols
- Informations non
- ONG, Centres de formations privés
- Consultants

Stateholders map and Requirements

(A) Summary of 3-groups

1 Decision makers
 Researchers + Lecturers
 Extension officers
 Private companies
 Funders
 Development organizations
 Media for awareness
 Farmer organisations.

2 - *to do research

- * for best land management and practice,
- * fertilizer recommendation
- * Strategic plan and long term goals.

3 -> updated data + Available data

- > Easy access data
- > standardized + harmonized data
- > Data sharing agreements
- > Data policies
- > Sustainable funding mechanisms
- > crop + soil + climate + roll out model

Stateholders map and Requirements

(B)

- Multi governance that bring national stakeholders to maintain and manage SIS.
- Identify different roles for national institutions in SIS.
- > Legal framework for how to share data /
- > Technical Supports.
- > Different languages /
- > Explore different system architectures.
- 4 -> Tools
- > Data management
- > Data series
- > awareness /
- > serving information for
- > How to use the system + maintain

Risks of Current Setup

- ① Not be able to continue access, manage, update own data.
- ② Political Risk between Countries can end the access.
- ③ Data lost
- ④ Invest time/resources/duplicate effort and set up anew SIS
- ⑤ To save the data on external hard disk.
- ⑥ or in a cloud.
- ⑦ or open access central Repositories.
- ⑧ use framework when we share the data to direct users.

- ⑨ The system is not-sustainable.
- ⑩ Data Damage is a risk.

Hosting Service

- ① National data Centre has the Tech and institutional capacity to host
- ② Digital economy ministry and digital agency.
national.
- ③ MoA has Services that can host data.
- ④ National agency for Cyber Security
- ⑤ national-private partnership is also an option

Annex 3: List of Participants

